

FAILURE MECHANICS OF SANDWICH PANELS SUBJECTED TO WATER SLAMMING

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich composite materials are widely used within the marine industry, particularly as hull panels. Water impact loads, known as slamming, can be very significant for these structures, particularly in high-speed craft. These loadings generate local regions of high transverse shear forces in the vicinity of panel boundaries, which can result in transverse shear fractures of core materials.

The aim of this paper is to characterise the failure mechanics of sandwich panels subjected to water slamming by comparing the failure modes and strength of sandwich panels to those expected from properties measured from individual material constituent coupons and sandwich beams. Core materials studied included cross-linked PVC, linear PVC, SAN foams and PET foams. Rectangular glass-fibre/epoxy skin sandwich panel specimens were impacted into a water surface at 10° deadrise angle at a constant velocity. The impact velocity was progressively increased until final failure of the panels. Panels were sectioned after the tests to determine their failure modes.

The results demonstrated significant differences in performance between low and high elongation materials, as well as differences in damage onset and final failure loads and modes depending on the type of core material. The more ductile foams performed better as panel structures under slamming relative to their quasi-static properties compared with the more brittle cores. Failure modes for the slam-loaded panels differed significantly between materials, but were similar to those from quasi-static and dynamic beam testing methods. The results support empirical experience that ductile foams perform well under slamming loads, and that high-elongation materials can perform better in slamming situations than predicted by their quasi-static strengths. The results also raise important questions about the relative importance of damage onset and residual strength of the panel structures, and about the most appropriate material parameters to characterise their suitability for slamming applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich composite materials are widely used within the marine industry, particularly as hull panels. Water impact loads, known as slamming, can be very significant for these structures, particularly for high-speed craft. These loadings generate local regions of high transverse shear forces in the vicinity of panel boundaries, which can result in transverse shear fractures of core materials. The transient nature of slamming loads means that the loads are applied very quickly (typically in the order of ms), which can cause stress rates that are high enough to affect the resulting strength of the core material, particularly for polymeric foams. Characterisation of sandwich structural behaviour is usually undertaken as constituent material coupons or sandwich beams, whereas most are actually used as panels.

Many commonly used foam core materials show an increase in strength under high strain rate loading, however there is no recognised method or standard for undertaking such testing for the purposes of material characterisation. The Det Norske Veritas Rules for Classification of High Speed, Light Craft and Naval Surface Craft [1] does specify a shear strength characterization test for the entire sandwich system based on four point loading of a sandwich beam including a longitudinal butt joint in the core at a nominal shear stress rate of 65 MPa/s. For these tests the resulting strength values are only to be used if they are lower than the static strength values; if they are higher, the static strength values must be used.

It is difficult to measure loading rates or strain rates on actual vessels, particularly because the highest core shear strain rates are likely to be localized in the vicinity of panel boundaries and related supporting structures. Measurements from full-scale trials were undertaken on the Swedish Navy's Visby Class corvette and reported by Burman, Rosen and Zenkert [2]. Results from tests in normal operating conditions included a maximum core transverse shear strain of 0.8% with a rate of 57/s corresponding to a stress rate of 59 MPa/s for the DIAB H250 Foam used. When extrapolated to the maximum allowable design strain of 2% this was estimated to be equivalent to a stress rate of between 120 to 254 MPa/s.

Controlled laboratory tests of sandwich panels have been also used by Battley et al. to estimate maximum core shear rates [3,4]. Strains measured on the skins of the sandwich panel were processed to provide estimates of core shear stress rates ranging from 217 to 2100 MPa/s depending on the water impact velocity. There is however, only limited data available on the performance of typical core materials at these loading rates. Studies by Daniels [5] and also by the current authors [4, 6] have demonstrated that loading rate does not significantly affect material stiffness, but can significantly affect material strength, with more ductile cores typically demonstrating higher strengths at elevated loading rates.

Beyond empirical knowledge of designers that high-elongation foams perform better under slamming loads than their static properties would predict, there is only very limited information about how the materials perform in an actual panel structure when subjected to water impact. The aim of this paper is to characterise the failure mechanics of sandwich panels subjected to water slamming, and compare the failure modes and strength of sandwich panels to those expected from properties measured from individual material constituent coupons or sandwich beams. This has been achieved by water impact testing of panel specimens in a specialised Servo-hydraulic Slam Testing System (SSTS), with monitoring of strains during tests and post-test sectioning of failed panels to characterise the core failure modes and loads.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

2.1 Test facility

The panel slamming experiments were undertaken using the University of Auckland's Servo-hydraulic Slam Testing System (SSTS). The SSTS uses a 3.5m diameter cylindrical water tank approximately half filled with 13,000L water. The specimen fixture (Figure 1) is attached to a vertically orientated hydraulic ram, and slides on linear bearings into the water, with the panel specimen able to be oriented at a range of deadrise angles (the angle between the panel and the water surface) of between zero to 40 degrees. Three fixed vertical panels; two on the sides and one behind the keel edge of the panel constrain the flow at three edges of the panel to represent a half-wedge of hull panelling. A key feature of the system is that the feedback controlled servo-hydraulic loading system enables repeatable impacts to be performed at a range of controlled velocities of up to approximately 10m/s. Further details of the system can be found in Battley and Allen [7].

(a) Schematic of loading fixture and flow restriction panels (b) Panel attached to loading fixture

Figure 1. Servo hydraulic Slam Testing System

2.2 Test specimens and instrumentation

Table 1 lists the six foams that were tested as panels, along with measured density for the actual materials tested and manufacturer's quoted shear strength and shear elongation. M80, M130, and G-PET 115 are manufactured by Gurit and C70-130, R63-140 and T90-320 by Airex AG.

C70-130 is a cross-linked polyvinyl chloride (PVC) foam that provides good stiffness and strength with moderate elongation. The M type foams are styrene-acrylonitrile (SAN) materials that have been developed as an alternative to PVC foams for marine and industrial applications. G-PET and T90.320 are polyethylene-terephthalate (PET) foams, which provide benefits of recyclability, formability and good thermal stability, but typically relatively low elongation to failure. R63-140 is a linear thermoplastic polymer foam with claimed high elongation and damage tolerance. The combination of materials and densities was selected to provide a range of different levels of ductility from the low-elongation PET cores through to the high-elongation linear foam.

It should be noted that the manufacturers of the core materials regularly update the formulations of their materials to enhance their performance, often without changing the material designations. It is hence possible for newer versions of such materials to have different performance than older samples. In particular, there have been significant changes in the properties of the G-PET foam, where the current similar density material (G-PET-110) now has a quoted manufacturer's shear elongation of 32%, significantly higher than the 7% for the material tested in this study.

The panel specimens (Figure 2) had external dimensions of 540 mm by 1030 mm, with an unsupported region between simply supported edges of 500 by 1000 mm. All of the cores had thicknesses of ~19 to 20mm. The laminates consisted of glass fibre/epoxy skins (3xEB825), with a skin thickness of approximately 2.4mm.

Core	Measured Density [kg/m ³]	Shear Strength [MPa]	Shear Elongation (%)
M80	86.1	1.09	58
M130	146	1.98	40
C70.130	147	2.3	30
R63.140	127	1.85	80
G-PET 115	119	0.94	7
T90.320	310	2.2	2.5

Table 1: Core material properties (Density measured, shear strength and elongation from manufacturer's data)

Figure 2: Panel Specimens

Each panel has been instrumented with two biaxial strain gauges (TML FCA-6-11 120 Ω), located as in Figure 3. The strain gauges are located at the centre of the unsupported region of the panel and 35 mm in from the chine edge of the panel. The chine edge is taken as the long edge of the panel that is submerged last. Subsequent to the tests the specimens were cut into sections A, B, C and D shown in Figure 3, each approximately 125 mm wide.

Figure 3: Instrumentation and cutting schematic, strain gauge directions denoted by arrows

2.3 Experimental test methodology

All testing for this work was undertaken with a deadrise angle of 10°. The first impact had a vertical impact velocity of 1.0 m/s. Each subsequent impact had an increase in target velocity of 0.5 m/s. The maximum impact velocities reached before final failure ranged from approximately 4 to 9 m/s depending on the core type. The maximum velocities were determined by monitoring failure of the panel visually and via the resistive strain gauges adhered to the inside skin of the panel.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Panel slam testing strain histories

Typical strain-time history results from slamming of an M80 core panel are presented in Figures 4 (2.5 m/s) and 5 (4 m/s). The strains in the 2.5 m/s impact (Figure 4) are representative of those occurring on panels prior to yield in the core. The transverse strain at the centre (y-direction, across short span of the panel) is the largest, as expected for a rectangular panel. The strain at the chine edge in the y-direction is lower and reaches its peak later than the strain at the centre, as the pressure pulse reaches this edge of the panel. The y direction strain trace at the chine is also more ‘peaked’ with a higher rate of strain increase than at the centre. The strain in the x-direction (along long span of the panel) is lower than in the y-direction at both the chine and the centre.

The strains in the 4.0 m/s impact (Figure 5) highlight how differently the panel behaves once some plastic deformation has occurred in the core. Of particular note is that the strain at the chine in the y-direction is non-zero at the start of the impact. This is an indicator of permanent deformation of the core leading to a localised change of shape for the panel at this edge, generating residual strains in the skin. The shape and magnitudes of the strain curves also differ significantly to those seen for the 2.5 m/s impact in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Strain-time history for M80 Panel at 2.5m/s

Figure 5. Strain-time history for M80 Panel at 4m/s

It can be seen that the strain in the y-direction is greater at the chine than at the centre for the 4.0 m/s impact. The longitudinal strain in the x-direction at the centre has also increased significantly relative to the y-direction, demonstrating that the panel is beginning to carry a larger portion of the load in the longitudinal direction. This is a result of core damage at the chine edge of the panel meaning that less load and hence moment can be carried across the shorter transverse span of the panel. In addition to its high magnitude, the chine edge strain in the y direction also has a high rate of increase as the pressure pulse reaches this region at the end of the slamming event.

3.2 Maximum strains vs. impact velocity

Figures 6 and 7 present the maximum strains at the centre of the panel relative to water impact velocity in the Transverse (y) and Longitudinal (x) directions. The maximum strain in the y direction (Figure 6) is similar for each of the panels at lower impact velocities as they all have approximately the same flexural stiffnesses. At higher velocities, panels with each type of core reach very different maximum transverse strain values, corresponding to damage (yield or fracture) occurring in the core materials. In most cases the maximum transverse strain value then decreases, as the damage progresses and the panels are less able to carry moments across the transverse direction. The first core material to

fail is the T90.320, followed by C70.130 and then M80. The R63.140 yields before the M130, but ultimately does not fracture within the range of impact speeds tested.

The centre strains in the longitudinal direction (Figure 7) are also similar between panels at low impact velocities. As failure occurs in the cores the longitudinal strains then start to increase as the panel carries more load along the long span. The progression of strain increases follows the same pattern as for the transverse strains in Figure 6. It can be noted that the strain for the R63.140 core starts to increase at a lower impact velocity than for the M130, even though both carry approximately the same maximum strain at the highest impact speeds reached. This is indicative of the earlier onset of yield in the R63.140 core than the M130.

Figure 6. Maximum strain at panel centre in transverse (y) direction relative to impact velocity

Figure 7. Maximum strain at panel centre in longitudinal direction (x) relative to impact velocity

Figures 8 and 9 present the maximum strains at the chine of the panel relative to water impact velocity in the Transverse (x) and Longitudinal (y) directions. In the y direction (Figure 15) the strains are as expected, approximately the same for all panels, then increase significantly as damage occurs in the core. The T90.320 is the first core to fail, the M80 appears to yield at approximately the same impact velocity as the C70.130 fractures, the R63.140 is the next core to yield, followed by the M130. The maximum strains at the chine edge are similar or higher than those reached at the panel centre, demonstrating the large amount of localised deformation occurring at the panel edge. A similar trend of relative failure order can be observed in the x direction strain (Figure 14), although the magnitudes are much lower.

Figure 8. Maximum strain at panel chine in transverse direction (y) relative to impact velocity

Figure 9. Maximum strain at panel chine in longitudinal direction (x) relative to impact velocity

3.2 Residual strains vs. impact velocity

For cores that yield and then undergo plastic deformation, the most effective way of identifying onset of damage to the core is by recording the residual strain following each successive water impact as shown in Figure 10. Onset of yield can be identified for the M80 core at approximately 4 m/s, R63.140 at approximately 4.5 m/s, and M130 at approximately 5.5 to 6 m/s. The G-PET 115, T90.320 and C70.130 cores all fail by fracture without significant yield, so there is no increase in residual strain, however the impact velocity at which the fracture occurred can be identified by the increase in maximum strain shown in Figure 8.

Figure 10. Residual strain at panel chine in transverse direction (y) relative to impact velocity

3.2 Fracture patterns

The panels were cut into sections after the tests in the positions shown in Figure 3 to determine the nature and position of the failures. Figure 11 shows the edges of the specimens at the failure regions.

(a) R63.140

(b) M80

(c) C70.130

(d) M130

(e) T92.320

Figure 11: Photos of sectioned panels showing through failure regions (chine edge on left)
(Order top to bottom from D to A)

The R63.140 cored panel underwent permanent transverse shear deformation without any core fracture. The M80 cored panel also underwent significant permanent transverse shear deformation, without any through-thickness core fracture, although there was a small region of skin-core delamination at the chine edge of the panel. The C70.140, M130 and T92 panels all had through thickness cracks, combined with associated skin/core delaminations. The positions of the through thickness cracks and the skin/core delaminations were measured and plotted, as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Schematics of sectioned panels showing fracture regions

The C70.140 panel fractured at the keel edge as shown in Figure 12 (a), with a continuous through thickness shear crack at approximately 45 degrees that was initially approximately parallel to the panel edge (sections D and C), then shifted towards the centre of the short edge at the end of the panel (Section A). There were significant regions of skin to core delaminations on both the top and bottom of the panel. There was also an additional small fracture region in the corner of the panel (top right in Figure 12(a)). The position of the fracture at the keel was unexpected, as it typically occurs at the more highly loaded chine edge, a sign that the core exceeded its failure strain prior to being completely submerged, suggesting that the velocity increment at failure may have been too large.

The M130 panel shown in Figure 12 (b) also had an approximately 45 degree shear fracture, although at the more typical chine edge. The fracture surface was not as straight or clearly defined as that for the C70 core, presumably due to the more ductile nature of the SAN foam. There was also significant skin/core delamination on both faces of the panel. The fracture region was reasonably parallel to the chine edge of the panel along the D, C and B sections, then diverged slightly away from the chine edge

as it reached the end of the panel in Section A. In the case of the T92 panel as shown in Figure 12 (c), the shear fracture was more perpendicular to the panel surface than for the other panels, and closer to the chine edge. The fracture did not progress very far past Section B, suggesting that this failure occurred due a single impact, without subsequent propagation.

One of the difficulties in interpreting these failures is that the panels were impacted several times after the onset of damage, so it is not possible to determine where the damage originated, or how much of the damage occurred in subsequent impacts. Additional specimens have been manufactured and will be tested in individual impacts at damage critical velocities to more accurately characterize the damage initiation and progression.

Figure 13 shows the failure regions of representative quasi-static and dynamic beam tests of the same materials [11]. The failure modes are generally similar between both types of beam testing and the water impact panel tests. In the case of R63.140 and M80 quasi-static and dynamic beams the core material undergoes significant permanent deformation prior to the final failure, which is a fracture of the upper skin of the sandwich in the vicinity of the loading point. The dynamically loaded M80 beam also suffered a shear fracture and skin-core fracture. The water impact loaded panels for these materials also underwent significant permanent deformation, with onset of skin/core fracture for the M80 material.

The C70.130 and M130 materials both failed by transverse shear fractures and associated skin-core fractures for both beam-loading situations. This failure mode was very similar for the panel specimens. The T90.320 material had very brittle transverse shear fractures in the beam tests, as was the case for the panels.

Figure 13: Failure regions of quasi-static and dynamic beam tests [11]

3.3 Core strength in slamming

The impact velocity at onset of core damage provides a qualitative ranking of the performance of the different core materials. To enable more quantitative comparisons it is necessary to relate the impact velocity to the transverse shear stress in the core. As the applied load distribution on the panels is not measured directly, it is necessary to calculate an approximation of the applied pressure in order to estimate the resulting shear stress in the core.

The approach taken in this work is described in [6]. An analytical solution for an equivalent static uniform pressure distribution is used based on the work of Payne [8]. For each of the panels, at the impact velocity at which the residual strains become non-zero, or the core fractures, an equivalent uniform pressure is calculated. The maximum transverse shear force is then calculated from based on classical sandwich panel theory from [9].

The applied transverse shear force, based on a uniform pressure, has been converted to an effective shear stress at core yield and used for comparison in Figure 14 (denoted “Uniform Pressure Slamming Yield”), which compares the apparent core shear stress at the onset of damage (yield or fracture) from the panel tests to those for corresponding quasi-static block shear, quasi-static beams and dynamic beam tests [4,6]. Figure 15 presents the same data normalised to the shear strength obtained from static beam test of the same foams.

Previous research has highlighted the effect of the non-uniformity of the pressure distribution on the maximum transverse shear force. Allen and Battley [10] showed the transverse shear force for this loading scenario was on average 78% higher than that predicted from a uniform pressure distribution. The calculated shear stress from this approach is also compared in Figures 14 and 15, denoted as “Modified Slamming Distribution”. While not the primary focus of this study, the results demonstrate that block shear tests can result in quite different quasi-static strengths than beam tests. In the case of the relatively brittle G-PET 115 and T90.320 cores the block shear strength is significantly lower than that measured for quasi-static beams, which may be due to the stress concentrations at the corners of the block shear specimens that are not present in beams.

The high-elongation R63.140 core has a much higher apparent strength in a block shear than as quasi-static beam due to the geometric changes during the block shear tests resulting in the test no longer being pure shear at high elongations, and the core carrying some load in tension. The M80, M130 and C70.130 cores have similar strengths in the block shear tests as in beams. The variation in measured shear strength depending on test method has important implications for the selection of materials for slamming applications, as consideration needs to be made of the type of test used by the manufacturer in preparation of their published data sheets, as well as the actual magnitudes of the properties.

The results shown in Figures 14 and 15 clearly demonstrate that the cores perform differently in a slam-loaded panel than as block shear coupons or beams. The more ductile M80, M130 and R63.140 foams perform better as a panel under slamming relative to their quasi-static beam properties compared with the more brittle cores. For a uniform load based analysis, each of the panels with more ductile foams (M80, M130 and R63.140) shows similar levels of improvement over a static beam test as was seen in dynamic beam testing. However once a non-uniform load is considered the improvement in apparent strength is even more substantial. Both M foams (80 and 130 kg/m³) have normalised apparent shear strengths in a panel of approximately 2.4 times their quasi-static strength.

While the R63.140 foam core panel yields at a lower impact velocity than the M130, its shear strength as a slam-loaded panel is approximately 3.5 times its static shear strength as a beam. The brittle foams demonstrated only slight improvement over static beam tests with normalised apparent shear strengths of 1.5 and 1.3 for G-PET 115 and T90.320 panels respectively. Despite C70.130 having the highest block shear, quasi-static and dynamic beam strengths, it is significantly less strong and more brittle as a slam-loaded panel than M130 or R63.140.

These results support empirical experience that ductile foams perform well under slamming loads, and that even with relatively low quasi-static shear strengths, high-elongation materials can perform better in slamming situations than less ductile materials that have higher quasi-static strengths.

For the more ductile cores, comparisons between M130 and R63.140 also raise important questions about the relative importance of damage onset (yield in these cases) and post-yield residual strength of the panel structures. The M130 yields at a higher impact velocity than the R63.140, but the core did ultimately fracture whereas the R63.140 panel underwent significant permanent deformation due to core plastic deformation, but remained intact.

Figure 14. Summary of apparent core shear strength depending on test method

Figure 15. Summary of apparent core shear strength depending on test method, normalised to static beam tests

4 CONCLUSIONS

The strength and failure modes of a range of polymeric foam core materials have been evaluated in controlled laboratory water impact testing, and compared to strengths measured by static and dynamic loading of coupon scale specimens. The results demonstrated significant differences in performance between low and high elongation materials, as well as differences in damage onset and final failure loads and modes depending on the type of core material.

The more ductile M80, M130 and R63.140 foams performed better as panel structures under slamming relative to their quasi-static properties compared with the more brittle G-

PET 115 and T90.320 foams demonstrated only slight improvement over quasi-static beam tests in slamming. Despite C70.130 having the highest block shear, quasi-static and dynamic beam strengths, it was significantly less strong and more brittle as a slam-loaded panel than M130 or R63.140.

Failure modes for the slam-loaded panels differed significantly between materials, but were similar to those from quasi-static and dynamic beam testing methods. In the case of R63.140 and M80 materials the failures were primarily permanent deformation of the core materials, with some fracture evident for the M80. The C70.130 and M130 materials both failed by transverse shear fractures and associated skin/core fractures, although the M130 material had significant permanent deformation prior to fracture. The T90.320 material had very brittle transverse shear fractures in the panel and beam tests.

The results support empirical experience that ductile foams perform well under slamming loads, and that high-elongation materials can perform better in slamming situations than predicted by their quasi-static strengths. The results also raise important questions about the relative importance of damage onset and residual strength of the panel structures, and about the most appropriate material parameters to characterise their suitability for slamming applications.

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